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SHORT COMMUNIAION

Photographic record of Rusty-spotted cat *Prionailurus rubiginosus* (Mammalia: Carnivora: Felidae) in Bonai Forest Division, Odisha, India

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ABSTRACT

Rusty-spotted cat is captured in Khusumdihi Reserve Forest, Tamra Range from Bonai Forest Division using camera trap. This captured is new record to the Bonai Forest Division, Sundargarh, Odisha. The photographs and habitat is provided.

A Rusty-spotted Cat was captured using camera trap on 11th October 2021 in Khusumdihi Reserve Forest, Tamra range, Bonai Forest Division, Odisha (Figure 1). It is a small felid that is endemic to India, Sri Lanka and Nepal. It is nocturnal and more arboreal in habits. Its preferred habitats are moist & dry deciduous forest, grassland and rarely sighted near human

settlement. Habitat loss and anthropogenic activities are major threats make it "Near threatened" species. In India, it is recorded from many states like Tamil Nadu, Kerala, Jammu & Kashmir, Madhya Pradesh, Gujarat etc (Mukerjee and Koparde 2014; Vimalraj et al. 2019). In Odisha state, it is reported from Sundergarh Forest Division, Debrigarh Wildlife Sanctuary, Baragarh

Forest Division, Hadagarh Wildlife Sanctuary, Satkosia Wildlife Division, Baliguda Forest Division, Kalahandi South Wildlife Division, Dukura range of Similipal, Hirakund Wildlife Division, Ghumusar North Forest Division, Phulbani Forest Division, Bolangir Forest Division and Katipada range, Similipal Tiger Reserve (Wriht 1984; Mishra et al. 2019; Palei et al. 2019). Hence the literature survey indicate that first time Rusty-spotted Cat is captured and recoded in Bonai Forest Division, Odisha.

Associated Faunal species: Jungle cat, Porcupine, Four horned antelope, Barking

deer, Grey Langur, Macaque, Asian Elephant, Mongoose, Leopard and Wild boar are recorded as a common associated faunal species from study areas.

Associated tree species: Sal (*Shorea robusta*), Asana (*Terminalia alata*), Mahula (*Madhuca longifolia*) and Chara (*Buchanania lanzan*) are recorded as a common associated tree species.

Vegetation: Sal dominant forest.

Observed threats: Anthropogenic activities, Grazing, hunting and feral dogs.

Figure 1: Occurrence record of Rusty-spotted cat in Bonai Forest Division, Odisha

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